

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D3.3 CONFIDENTIAL MULTI-PARTY AI/ML

PROJECT INFORMATION

Call	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022
Type of Action	HORIZON-JU-RIA HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
Project start date	01/01/2023
Duration	36 months
GA No	101096435

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Deliverable WP:	WP3
Deliverable Task:	Task T3.3
Deliverable Identifier:	CONFIDENTIAL6G_D3.3
Deliverable Title:	CONFIDENTIAL MULTI-PARTY AI/ML
Editor(s):	TNO
Author(s):	TUW, IMD, NOK, NNF, TNO, UVC, WINGS
Reviewer(s):	IMD, WINGS
Contractual Date of Delivery:	30/06/2025
Submission Date:	03/07/2025
Dissemination Level:	PU
Status:	Final
Version:	1.0
File Name:	CONFIDENTIAL6G_D3.3_Confidential_Multi-party_AI-ML_v1.0

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DRAFT

DOCUMENT LOG

VERSION	DATE	DESCRIPTION OF CHANGE
V1.0	03/07/2025	Final version, submitted to EC through SyGMa

DRAFT

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CLI	Command Line Interface
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CVM	Confidential Virtual Machine
DKG	Distributed Key Generation
FHE	Fully Homomorphic Encryption
HAL	Hardware Abstraction Layer
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
NN	Neural Network
OBU	On Board Unit
PET	Privacy Enhancing Technology
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
ThFHE	Threshold Fully Homomorphic Encryption
TPM	Trusted Platform Modul
VM	Virtual Machine
VMPL	Virtual Machine Privilege Level
WNN	Weightless Neural Network
ZKP	Zero Knowledge Proof

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on the work done in Task 3.3. More specifically, this report explains concepts and mechanisms for collaborative AI/ML and discusses approaches using Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE). Additionally, software building blocks on verifiable computations are developed and detailed.

In Section 2, we consider the relation between Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) and AI. We describe which components of a TEE are relevant to facilitate collaboration on AI/ML. After that, Section 3 is concerned with how FHE can be used in an AI context. More particularly, we provide the background for this application, consider some technical details and provide experimental results as well. In Section 4, we dive into the third technology and its relation to AI: the notion of verifiability through (succinct) cryptographic proofs. We provide two ways in which verifiability might be used in an AI context: how to verify a server's computation on FHE-encrypted data in a client-server model, and how to verify other parties' computations in a federated learning context. Lastly, in Section 5, we consider two use cases relevant for the technologies discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 SCOPE AND RELATION TO D2.3

The purpose of this document is to report on the work done in Task 3.3, revolving around collaborative AI/ML. More specifically, we consider three technologies: Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) and Verifiable Computation using Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs). For each, we consider how these technologies are relevant for AI.

We note that there is a strong connection between this deliverable (D3.3) and Deliverable 2.3 entitled “Confidential Computation Toolkit”. In a clear sense, D3.3 can be said to build on the results from D2.3. More specifically, the technologies discussed in the present context (and applied to AI) have already been introduced and discussed at length in D2.3. Indeed, some of the building blocks developed and described in the context of D2.3 are directly relevant for the AI use case. Therefore D2.3 is referenced explicitly throughout this report.

1.2 DOCUMENT ORGANIZATION

In each of the following three Sections, we consider a specific privacy enhancing technology and how it relates or might in the future relate to AI. The technologies are TEEs (Section 2), FHE (Section 3) and verifiable computing (Section 4). In the final section, we consider two applications of the discussed technologies to realistic use cases, in an effort to illustrate how these technologies might be used in practice. In the Appendix A : Test cases we sketch some test cases for TEE, FHE and verifiability components. While the actual testing is done in the context of a different Task within CONFIDENTIAL6G, we include the test cases here for the sake of completeness.

2 TRUSTED EXECUTION ENVIRONMENTS & AI

A Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) is a separate part of the main memory and the CPU that encrypts code/data and enables "on the fly" executions of the said encrypted code/data. Multiple industry-leading companies, such as AMD and Intel, provide their versions of TEEs. While Intel started with Software Guard Extensions (SGX), which protects only a predefined part of a process, AMD started with TEEs that protect whole virtual machines (VMs). AMD SEV and its latest and most secure iteration, AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization - Secure Nested Paging (SEV-SNP), is a technology that isolates the entire VM. This approach of isolating an entire VM leads to what is called a confidential VM (CVM). SEV-SNP encrypts the whole VM and provides confidentiality and integrity protection of the VM memory. This way, the hypervisor or any other application on the host machine cannot read the VM memory.

TEEs are increasingly being combined with AI because of their security and privacy-preserving nature. Combining TEEs with AI allows users to train their AI models using sensitive data. For example, hospitals can provide sensitive patient data to TEEs so that AI models can be trained on the said data.

In the next sections, we will look at the components developed in work packages 2 and 3 that are used to define the workflow for the use of AI and TEEs and the workflow that facilitates the use of AI in TEEs.

2.1 COMPONENTS THAT HELP FACILITATE THE USE OF AI IN TEEs

In this section, we will define the components needed for running AI in components defined in work packages 2 and 3, mainly the TEE toolkit defined in D2.3. The defined components allow users to form consortiums, send data and algorithms to TEEs, and fetch the results.

2.1.1 HARDWARE ABSTRACTION LAYER

The hardware abstraction layer, or HAL, is a programming layer that allows the software to interact with the hardware device at a general level rather than at the detailed hardware level. HAL can be used with AMD SEV-SNP to provide an abstraction layer to execute confidential algorithms and receive confidential data securely.

To keep the HAL small and not use a whole VM (e.g., Ubuntu), HAL is made of:

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- Linux kernel with support for AMD SEV in guest.
- Initial RAM file system (initramfs)
- Open Virtual Machine Firmware (OVMF)
- Kernel command line
- Virtual Trusted Platform Module (vTPM)

Linux and the initial RAM file system are enough to create a functioning environment to help train AI models.

A TPM is a physical or embedded security technology that resides on the motherboard or in the processor. The TPM uses cryptography to securely store and protect essential and critical information on PCs, enabling device authentication. TPM is used to verify the boot process from trusted hardware and software.

The vTPM is part of the HAL, thanks to the AMD SEV-SNP technology, which introduces Virtual Machine Privilege Levels (VMPLs). VMPLs are hardware-assisted abstraction layers. There are four VMPLs with descending privilege levels, with VMPL0 being the most privileged and VMPL3 being the least privileged. Software running at a more privileged VMPL level can access the less privileged VMPL level. The vTPM is running in VMPL0, while the Linux kernel and the initial RAM file system are running inside VMPL2. This way, the software from VMPL2 cannot access the software in VMPL0, meaning the vTPM cannot be tampered with.

2.1.2 MANAGER

The Manager is a software component whose role is to create and manage CVMs. The Manager must be running on a server capable of creating TEEs. Another role of the Manager is to provide the CVM with certificates and configuration data.

2.1.3 AGENT

The Agent is a component that runs inside the CVM. The Agent's primary role is to provide an interface to the CVM that users can use to communicate with the CVM. Using this interface, the users can send data and an algorithm to the Agent, which then the Agent can run and return the results to the designated result consumers.

Another crucial role of the Agent is to provide proof that it is running inside a CVM (TEE). This process is done using remote attestation. During remote attestation, the Agent provides the users of the CVM with a report (attestation report) that gives them information on the HAL, like the software running inside the CVM and the hardware the CVM is running on. The attestation report is used to assure users that the CVM is running in a genuine hardware TEE.

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2.1.4 COMPUTATION MANAGEMENT

Computation management is a service that is used to create the computation. It creates a file that contains the following information: the hash of the algorithm, information on the providers of the algorithm, the datasets, and the result consumer. This information is needed so that the Agent knows with whom it can communicate.

2.1.5 COMMAND LINE INTERFACE (CLI) APPLICATION

The CLI allows users to communicate with the Agent inside the CVM. The CLI is used to send data and an algorithm to the Agent and verification of the attestation report from the Agent.

2.2 EXECUTION FLOW

The execution flow comprises all the aforementioned components. Figure 1 shows the Agent, the HAL, and an example of hospitals sending their data to the Agent for processing.

Figure 1: Agent communication within HAL

When the Agent receives the computation manifest, it goes through a couple of states. They are:

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- **Idle:** Initial state of the Agent. The Agent is in this state for a very short period of time. In this state, the service of the Agent is being initialized.
- **Manifest** (or Receiving manifest state): In this state, the Agent waits for the computation management to send it the computation manifest file.
- **Algorithm** (or Receiving algorithm state): In this state, the Agent is waiting to receive the algorithm from the algorithm provider, and when it gets the algorithm, it checks if the algorithm is from the user defined in the computation manifest.
- **Datasets** (or Receiving datasets state): In this state, the Agent is waiting to receive all the datasets. Upon receiving each dataset, the Agent checks if the dataset is from the appropriate dataset provider.
- **Running state:** The Agent runs the algorithm.
- **Results ready state:** In this state, the algorithm has finished running and is ready to send results to the appropriate results consumers.
- **Complete state:** After all the results have been sent to the appropriate result consumers, the Agent enters the complete state and waits for the stop computation event from the computation management so it can go to the idle state.
- **Failed state:** The Agent arrives in this state when an error occurs at any time during the execution of the computation. From this state, the Agent can go to the idle state when it receives the stop computation event from the computation management component.

In Figure 2, the state transition is illustrated.

Figure 2: Execution Flow State

3 FULLY HOMOMORPHIC ENCRYPTION & AI

We aim to formally and intuitively describe Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) and Machine Learning (ML). We will then describe the relationship between these two fields and the challenges and solutions associated with that.

3.1 PRIMER ON FULLY HOMOMORPHIC ENCRYPTION

Fully homomorphic encryption (FHE), first introduced in 2009 [1] represents a significant advance in cryptographic methodology, enabling computations on encrypted data without disclosing the underlying information. This technique is of great importance for the preservation of data privacy in a number of sectors, including cloud computing, healthcare, and finance. It eliminates the need to decrypt sensitive data during processing, which is crucial for the protection of personal information. In the realm of artificial intelligence and machine learning, FHE allows for the secure training and inference of models on encrypted datasets. This ensures the confidentiality of data and compliance with privacy regulations. This capability is particularly crucial for the development of privacy-preserving AI applications, which foster trust and expand the scope of secure data utilization.

In a nutshell, FHE allows to encrypt information in a way that a function can be evaluated on the plaintext by executing an evaluation algorithm on the ciphertext. The decryption of the corresponding output of the evaluation should then correspond to the function evaluated on the plaintext. In order to gain an understanding of the mechanics and applications of fully homomorphic encryption, it is essential to describe the scheme in a formal manner on an abstract level. This formal description enables us to comprehend the underlying processes, establish a clear framework, and set the necessary notation for discussing the encryption scheme's components and operations:

Definition (Fully Homomorphic Encryption Scheme): A public key homomorphic encryption scheme E consists of four (probabilistic) polynomial time algorithms $E = (Gen, Enc, Dec, Eval)$ such that:

1. The key-generation algorithm $(sk, pk) \leftarrow Gen(1^\lambda)$ takes as input a security parameter 1^λ (in unary) and outputs a secret key sk , a public key pk , and a (public) evaluation key evk .
2. The encryption algorithm $(c) \leftarrow Enc(pk, m)$ takes as input a public key pk and a message m and outputs a ciphertext c .
3. The decryption algorithm $(m) \leftarrow Dec(sk, c)$ takes as input a secret key sk and a ciphertext c and outputs a message m .
4. The evaluation algorithm $Eval$ takes as input the evaluation key evk , a function f , and t -tuple of ciphertexts (c_1, \dots, c_t) and outputs a ciphertext c_f so that $c_f = Eval(evk, f, (c_1, \dots, c_t))$ and $Dec(sk, c_f) = f(m_1, \dots, m_t)$.

3.2 PRIMER ON MACHINE LEARNING

Machine learning (ML) is the branch of computer science concerned with enabling machines to find solutions to problems on their own. Let's look at an example. Suppose the target problem is computing the greatest common divisor (gcd) between two integers. This is a fundamental problem in number theory, and there are several detailed algorithms that solve it. It is intuitive to exploit the mathematical properties of the greatest common divisor (gcd) to design an exact algorithm. This approach, i.e., solving the problem exactly, has been standard in computer science for centuries. However, there are cases in which this is unfeasible. Consider the problem of recognizing pictures of cats (i.e., given some input image, determine whether it contains a cat). Using the traditional approach, one must first define what a cat is, then infer exact rules to distinguish cats from other objects and finally hardcode these rules into software. This process is excruciating, and the initial steps require precise definitions that are likely to be extremely complex. The ML paradigm circumvents these problems by designing *learning* algorithms. These algorithms extract knowledge from data and use it to produce a fine-tuned algorithm capable of solving the target problem.

ML is often informally split into three subfields:

- **Supervised learning:** The learning algorithm is guided by attaching labels to each datum. These labels provide additional information for the learning process and act as a sort of "teacher." In our example with cat images, we could give our algorithm a set of images and assign a label, taking binary

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values to each image. The label tells the algorithm whether the image contains a cat.

- **Unsupervised learning:** The algorithm is not guided, but must find patterns and regularities in the data on its own. In our example, suppose the learning algorithm is supplied with images of animals. The algorithm could recognize similar images by just recognizing similarities in the pixels, without any external aid.
- **Reinforcement learning:** An agent learns how to solve a problem through a system of penalties and rewards. For example, we could reward the image recognizer when it identifies a cat and penalize it when it misclassifies an image.

Furthermore, it is crucial to clarify the type of task whenever a machine has to learn a new one. This has significant consequences for the training and validation phases, to name a few. We broadly and informally classify problems as follows:

- **Regression:** Given an input x , predict an associated target value y taking value in a continuous set. For instance, predicting the top speed of a car given some of its core features is a regression problem.
- **Classification:** Given an input x , predict an associated target value y taking value in a discrete set. For instance, the aforementioned image recognition problem is a binary classification problem.

In the ML framework, the final prediction on input x is often in the form $f_w(x)$, where w is a vector of real parameters of dimension d . A supervised learning algorithm aims at deriving a "nice" parameter vector from a dataset. The latter consists of input-label pairs $S = \{(x_i, y_i) | i \in [n]\}$ drawn from some unknown distribution D . We will, informally, extract information on the unknown distribution D from the provided dataset, and then encode this information in the vector w . In practice, how is this done?

While the specific method is highly algorithm-dependent, from a high-level viewpoint, most of them leverage a so-called *loss function*. The latter receives a dataset and a candidate as inputs, and outputs a real number that quantifies how good the candidate is. The smaller, the better. The loss function is again non-trivially dependent on the algorithm and the type of problem. As a rule of thumb, one can use an L1 or L2 loss for regression problems and the cross-entropy loss for classification problems. Then, the main idea is to search for a vector w for which the loss function is as small as possible. This is achievable through a plethora of optimization and search algorithms, each with its own pros and cons. In practice, after fixing a dataset and a loss function, you run an optimization algorithm that

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finds parameters w yielding a low enough loss function. This process is often called *training* and is notoriously computationally intensive, often requiring specialized hardware such as expensive GPUs or TPUs. Even on such sophisticated components, training can take hours or days. Furthermore, training requires as much data as possible. Intuitively, the more records a model sees, the greater its final ability to make trustworthy predictions on new samples.

Said learning algorithms perform exceptionally well in practice, sometimes even too well. Overfitting is an undesirable phenomenon in ML that causes a learning algorithm to learn exceptionally well the training set, but without acquiring the necessary generalization ability to predict anything when exposed to new data. As a high-level example, imagine a student, Bob, who is studying for an exam on quadratic equations. Following a horrible strategy, suppose Bob memorizes by heart all the quadratic equations in his textbook and their numerical solutions, completely disregarding the underlying math. If we interrogate Bob on those equations, he will answer each question perfectly and timely. However, as soon as he sees a new equation, Bob is completely lost and won't know how to answer. A similar event can occur for ML models. Practitioners are well aware of this and tackle this in several ways. The techniques are generally algorithm-dependent, and we limit ourselves to a broad classification based on the intended goal:

- **Detection:** Some methods are, essentially, algorithms to detect the occurrence of overfitting. Once detected, we can stop the learning process or take appropriate countermeasures.
- **Regularization:** We modify the original learning algorithm to prevent overfitting.

Detection methods often require an additional dataset, known as a validation dataset. From a high-level viewpoint, we use that to continuously monitor the generalization ability of a model under training. The model is trained using a training set and iteratively tested using the validation set. In particular, the model never learns from the validation set. Then, if a model performs exceptionally well on the training set but poorly on the validation set, we can conclude that overfitting has occurred, and stop training. This may save computational resources, but it introduces an additional demand for data.

3.3 INTERACTION BETWEEN FHE AND ML

Machine Learning is highly data-intensive. Training an algorithm requires huge amounts of data to ensure that the output model has high enough generalization capabilities. Unfortunately, this comes with non-trivial privacy issues. The training

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data is often associated with real people and must be collected in some node to run the training phase. This process is not privacy-preserving, in general, as whoever owns the server where the training algorithm is run can just inspect the collected data. What if the latter contains medical records or other sensitive information?

Similar concerns arise after training. Suppose there is a publicly accessible ML model, perhaps owned and maintained by a big company, that computes predictions upon receiving customers' requests. In practice, customers must share their data with the company, which then runs the prediction process on its servers and returns the result to customers. Once again, the inputs to the ML model could contain sensitive information, and nothing would prevent the company from accessing that.

Figure 3: Encoding, encrypting and evaluating in CKKS. Taken from [2].

FHE is a powerful ally in this setting. The remarkable ability to perform computation on encrypted data enables the training of a ML model over encrypted data. Analogously, one can run predictions on encrypted data. Therefore, we get the best of both worlds: the transformative power of AI, at no cost in privacy. We provide an overview of the common workflow in Figure 3.

As convenient as this may sound, the process comes with many non-trivial challenges. First of all, ML and FHE are both incredibly demanding when run independently. Their combination is even more expensive. To effectively run FHE-

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based privacy-preserving ML, simply combining techniques from the two fields is often not satisfactory. For this reason, intensive research is taking place, searching for more efficient solutions. Another efficiency issue arises due to mathematical incompatibilities between the two frameworks. Many FHE schemes were designed with the goal of performing Boolean computations over ciphertexts. In other words, most FHE algorithms expect bits. On the other hand, many ML algorithms are inherently defined over a field of real numbers. Of course, one can approximate real numbers using floating point arithmetic and view ML algorithms as a sequence of Boolean operations. While this works, it introduces an efficiency problem. That is, this approach is often not computationally feasible. Recent works have designed and validated new FHE algorithms that address this issue. For instance, the popular CKKS algorithm is a beautiful FHE algorithm designed to compute over encrypted complex numbers (and therefore, encrypted real numbers too). This is achieved by embedding complex numbers into a ring of polynomials and leveraging results in lattice cryptography to encrypt said ring elements and homomorphically combine them. A high-level overview is provided in the above figure. Without going into the mathematical details, this provides a fast and flexible method that, despite still discretizing real numbers, is much more efficient than the aforementioned naive solutions.

The potential of this idea is immense. Indeed, CKKS is not just a theoretical algorithm; it is implemented, and adopted in many groundbreaking frameworks. For instance, CryptoLab Inc recently released the “Encrypted LLM Experience”, which “enables developers to build their own encrypted LLM providing the flexibility to implement custom functions such as a tailored softmax, while leveraging homomorphic encryption for secure computations on sensitive data” [3]. Similarly, the recently released HEaaN.Stat SDK which “features a Python library that enables data analysts to perform a range of statistical functions directly on encrypted data. Built on the HEaaN CKKS library, HEaaN.Stat enables privacy-preserving analysis without revealing sensitive information, making it a powerful tool for industries requiring strong data privacy, such as healthcare, finance, and government” [4].

Crucially, CKKS (as well as other FHE schemes) leverages lattice-based cryptography, which is (to the best of our knowledge) quantum-safe. In particular, it is not vulnerable to quantum attacks based on the quantum Fourier Transform, which threaten classical RSA and discrete-logarithm based cryptosystems. Furthermore, the recent developments lead to significant efficiency improvements, in particular thanks to the switch from integer lattices to ideal lattices. Traditional lattice-based cryptography required expensive matrix multiplications and larger

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keys/ciphertexts due to working with large integer vectors. For a long time, this caused lattice cryptography to be rather impractical. Thanks to meaningful research efforts, it is now feasible to instead work in a ring of polynomials (akin to what is shown in Figure 3) and still recycle the previous hardness assumptions (although, theoretically, we are now relying on their ideal-lattice version). This has a remarkable impact on practicality, leading to more compact keys/outputs and faster computations. This new paradigm makes lattice-based FHE, and its applications to ML, more than a theoretical wonderland: FHE-enabled privacy preserving ML is possible, feasible, and it is already usable via public implementations. Here, we present a (non-exhaustive) list of some well-known FHE libraries:

- [OpenFHE](#) is an open source project that contains C++ implementations of all leading FHE schemes (BGV, BFV, CKKS, FHEW, TFHE and LMKCDEY). It also contains a number of examples, tools for multi-party extensions and Python and Rust wrappers.
- [Zama](#) is an open source cryptography company focused on building FHE solutions for AI and blockchain applications. They offer an implementation of TFHE in Rust, as well as many AI-oriented demos.
- [MOSFHET](#) is an optimized open source implementation of TFHE, which has been developed in the context of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. We refer to Deliverable 2.3 of this project for more details.
- [SEAL](#) is an open source library for FHE by Microsoft. Although some researchers still use it, it is not being maintained (to the same degree as the other libraries listed here).
- [HELib](#) is another open source library for FHE, but like SEAL, it does not appear to be maintained.

3.4 FHE FOR TRAINING AND EVALUATING ML

As discussed previously, modern HE schemes are capable of efficiently performing encrypted inference with near state-of-the-art accuracy even on very large neural network models. This is a result, in part, of the use of techniques such as quantized training [5] and FHE-friendly activation functions [6]. Efficient and accurate encrypted training, on the other hand, is a significantly more difficult problem, as current solutions either stay far from state-of-the-art accuracy levels or take weeks of computation to be run [7]. Some scenarios allow for alternative approaches, such as client-assisted FHE [8] and other MPC-based protocols, which may offer

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good results in limited contexts but come with the intrinsic downsides of multi-party protocols. On another direction, some solutions for encrypted training rely on techniques such as transfer learning and cleartext feature extraction, which also do not allow for the full secure outsourcing of computation. In these cases, a pre-trained model or feature extraction algorithm is applied over the unencrypted input data before the encrypted training. This approach has often been employed to accelerate or improve the accuracy of encrypted training [7] [9] [10]. However, its application is limited as it requires the existence of a pre-trained model that works for the specific problem. This model needs to be trained and evaluated on cleartext, requiring additional security and usability assumptions. It requires, for example, the data owner to perform part of the training (the feature extraction) on cleartext in a trusted environment before encrypting the input data, which might be prohibitive in the case of resource-constrained clients.

For end-to-end fully encrypted training, the most practical approaches so far go in the direction of adopting simpler ML algorithms or methods for switching between different HE schemes. In 2019, NRPH19 [11] presented the first stochastic-gradient-descent-based (SGD) approach for encrypted Neural Network (NN) training, achieving accuracies of 85.9% up to 97.8% on inferences on the MNIST dataset [12]. Their execution time, however, would be up to more than a decade. Using HE scheme switching, Chimera [13] [14] and Glyph [7] improved this result significantly, enabling accuracies of 94.1% up to 97.1% with execution times between 5.7 and 28.6 days for the former and between 1.5 and 8 days for the latter. Recently, MFK+24 [15] presented a TFHE-based evaluation of a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) training for the Wisconsin breast cancer dataset [16], achieving 98.25% accuracy in 49 minutes.

3.4.1 COMMON MACHINE LEARNING DATASETS

Many machine learning datasets have been adopted as benchmarks across literature. For encrypted inference, relatively large datasets, such as ImageNet [17] are often adopted, whereas for encrypted training, small datasets, such as Wisconsin [16], are preferred due to the current performance limitations of FHE. In this work, we consider the following datasets:

- MNIST [12]: comprises 70000 grayscale images of handwritten digits, each sized at 28×28 pixels.
- HAM10000 [18]: also known as Skin Cancer MNIST or DermaMNIST, consists of 10015 RGB images representing seven types of skin conditions.

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- Wisconsin Breast Cancer [16]: a tabular dataset containing 569 samples, each of them featuring 30 attributes of breast cell nuclei for breast cancer classification, categorized into benign and malignant.

3.4.2 TFHE-BASED ENCRYPTED TRAINING

CKKS is the most used scheme for the encrypted evaluation of machine learning algorithms, having been developed specifically for this purpose. Its performance, however, often relies on levelled homomorphic evaluations, which restricts its use for encrypted training where bootstrapping is usually required. GSW-based schemes, on the hand, typically work with bootstrapped evaluations and are often seen as a good alternative for efficient encrypted training. Compared to CKKS, they typically provide good latency but have limited throughput of operations, which restricts their use to much smaller machine learning models. Table 1 summarizes the use of TFHE, which is a state-of-the-art GSW-based scheme, for evaluating encrypted inference over the MNIST dataset. Note that approach called WiSARD, discussed in more detail in 3.4.3, as well as the following tables stem from [19], which was contributed to in the context of this project.

Table 1: Summary of TFHE-based encrypted inference for the MNIST model. Data from [19].

Solution	Accuracy (%)	Time (s)	Security	Threads
DiNN [13]	93.71	0.49	80	1
DiNN [13]	96.3	1.5	80	1
SFB ⁺ 23 [20]	92.2	31	128	16
SFB ⁺ 23 [20]	96.5	77	128	16
SHE [21]	99.54	9.3	128	20
REDsec [22]	98	12.3	128	96
REDsec [22]	99	18.4	128	96
Hom. WiSARD [19] S	91.4	0.774 (0.048)	128	1 (128)
Hom. WiSARD [19] M	92.81	1.47 (0.067)	128	1 (128)
Hom. WiSARD [19]L	93.43	2.184 (0.092)	128	1 (128)

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Compared with the performance provided by methods using CKKS, which are presented in Table 2, TFHE-based encrypted inference can be faster in latency, but generally presents lower accuracy and up to 4 orders of magnitude lower throughput. On the positive side, as it is typically based on bootstrapped evaluation, it might be more suitable for encrypted training, especially for relatively small datasets.

Table 2: Examples of CKKS-based encrypted inference for the MNIST model.

	Accuracy	Time	Batch size	Security	Threads
CDKS19 [23]	98.4	1.8s	1	128	1
ISY20 [6]	99.29	21.15s	8192	128	16

3.4.3 ENCRYPTED ML TRAINING

Large machine learning models, such as deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs), are very powerful tools for data processing and can be employed in many real-world use cases. Considering that, their homomorphic evaluation is often seen as a major goal for the privacy-preserving machine learning community. In practice, however, only relatively small CNNs have been homomorphically evaluated, as their computation cost is already at order of weeks of computation. More practical results can be achieved when considering lightweight machine learning approaches, such as Support Vector Machine (SVMs), Multilayer Perceptron's (MLPs), and Weightless neural networks (WNNs).

As part of this project, we contributed to the development of the Homomorphic WiSARDs framework [19](currently on open [arXiv](#); accepted at ACNS 2025), which provides efficient encrypted training for Weightless Neural Networks (WNNs). In contrast with typical NNs, neurons of WNNs are just lookup tables or Random Access Memory (RAM) units, which evaluate arbitrary discretized functions over data they receive. There are no weights or biases, and the training consists of programming the RAM units to evaluate different functions that will (hopefully) recognize categorizing patterns in the input data. One of the most basic instantiations of a WNN and the starting point of the Homomorphic WiSARDs framework is Wilkie, Stonham, and Aleksander's Recognition Device (WiSARD) [24]. In their model, RAM units are programmed to simply output whether a certain pattern of bits (the neuron's input) was present in the training set for a certain label. Modern WNNs employ significantly more complex functions, but the basic principle of programming RAM units remains their defining aspect. The Homomorphic

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WiSARDs framework [19] starts from the observation that operating with RAM units fits perfectly well within the computation model provided by schemes such as FHEW and TFHE, which are based on the evaluation of lookup tables (LUTs). In this way, it is able to provide efficient encrypted training for many image classification problems for which CNN would be too slow. Table 3 summarizes the main solutions for encrypted machine learning training using CNNs, WNNs, and other lightweight approaches.

Table 3: Summary of encrypted training. Data from [19]

Dataset	Solution	Accuracy (%)	Time
MNIST	Hom. WiSARD WNN [19] S	91.71%	3m28s
	Hom. WiSARD WNN [19] M	93.06%	38m18s
	Hom. WiSARD WNN [19] L	93.76%	3h30m
	Glyph CNN [7]	94.10%	1.5d
	Glyph CNN [7]	97.10%	8d
HAM10000	Hom. WiSARD WNN [19] S	67.85%	1m35s
	Hom. WiSARD WNN [19] M	68.60%	13m35s
	Hom. WiSARD WNN [19] L	69.85%	1h03m
	Glyph CNN [7]	69.20%	7d
Wisconsin	Hom. WiSARD WNN [19]	97.30%	316ms
	PBL+20 SVM [25]	98.00%	5m34s
	MFK+24 MLP [15]	98.25%	49m

As one would expect, CNNs present significantly better results in terms of accuracy, but lightweight approaches have a relatively small accuracy drop when considering they are up to 3 orders of magnitude faster. In particular, for some problems such as HAM10000, the Homomorphic WiSARDs framework was capable of being more accurate than Glyph's CNNs while also being much faster. While this can be seen as unexpected at first, considering CNNs are vastly more powerful than WNNs, this is a common occurrence in slightly larger problems, such as the

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HAM10000. In these cases, while CNNs would indeed provide better accuracy on cleartext, their homomorphic evaluation requires them to be simplified for performance, which incurs accuracy drops often larger than the ones of lightweight approaches.

DRAFT

4 VERIFIABLE COMPUTATION & AI

In this Section, we will discuss applications of verifiable computation to AI. As detailed in D2.3, verifiable computation is concerned with the application of (zero-knowledge) proofs to provide integrity for outsourced calculations. By attaching a proof to a computation result, the computing party can prove to the client that they performed the appropriate calculations.

NB: Cryptographic proofs are often discussed in the context of privacy. Indeed, a focal point of this research area has been around so-called zero-knowledge proofs (ZKPs), in which an entity can prove a claim without revealing the underlying data. In the context of verifiability however, zero-knowledge properties are not the primary goal or even used at all: here, the point of a proof is for a verifier to check a calculation without having to redo the calculation. While the techniques are similar (indeed, zero-knowledge properties can often be added with little extra cost), we note that many of the following techniques are not, strictly speaking, ZKPs.

In this section, we consider two types of interactions between verifiable computation and AI. First, we discuss verifiable FHE: how clients might be able to verify that the AI computation they outsourced (under FHE) to a server was performed correctly. After that, we consider a federated learning setting: how can clients verify from each other that they are cooperating properly.

4.1 VERIFIABLE FHE

As described in the previous Section, the use of Fully Homomorphic Encryption can address many of the privacy challenges that come with the processing of sensitive data with machine learning.

Unfortunately, Fully Homomorphic Encryption does not provide, by itself, guarantees of *integrity* in these applications. Even if the parameters of the ML model are public, the tasks of evaluating, and especially, training, this model are usually too computationally intensive for a client to be carried out on their own (in fact this is often the reason why this computation is delegated to a server, and why we need FHE to guarantee privacy in the first place) and therefore it is hard for a client to verify that the computation has been carried out correctly.

Moreover, integrity is not only a functional requirement, but it also can affect privacy: consider for example the case in which training of a ML model is being carried out on encrypted data coming from multiple parties, resulting in an encrypted ML model. Anyone can perform any type of computation over this model,

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but parties must agree (e.g. via a small MPC protocol) before declassifying any information. In this case, parties may be willing to decrypt some inference on the client's data, but not part of the model. Therefore, it is essential to be able to verify what computation is being evaluated on the encrypted model.

Verifiable computation on fully homomorphically encrypted data would allow to verify that the output ciphertext corresponds indeed to the result of applying the permitted computation, so that decrypting the result will yield the desired value.

During this project, we have made significant contributions to progress beyond the state of the art of verifiable computation on data encrypted with FHE scheme, which have been accepted in two major conferences in cryptography, highlighting the importance of this area. We discuss these results in detail in Section 5.1 of D2.3 and only provide a brief summary here. The first publication [26] is a general approach for so called exact FHE schemes, that was published in ASIACRYPT 24. However, this approach cannot support HE schemes for arithmetic of approximate numbers, like CKKS. Moreover, their verification procedure requires a secret key and they operate in a weaker adversarial model where the verifier must keep secret whether verification passes (as otherwise a malicious server can figure out information about the secret key), which hampers its application to many ML scenarios. Our second contribution focuses on the case of data encrypted with CKKS and will appear at Crypto 25 [27]. As was mentioned in Section 3, the CKKS Fully Homomorphic Encryption scheme has been implemented to run, among other applications, LLM in an encrypted fashion, which motivates our attention to improving verifiable computation on this encryption scheme.

A good analysis of state-of-the art prior to our works was given in [28], and concluded that current solutions for verifiable computation on HE typically incur prohibitive costs for the server, due to fundamentally two factors: one is the algebraic domain where ciphertext operations are carried out; these are algebraic polynomial rings, whereas proof systems are usually designed for finite fields, which creates some overhead in transferring operations from one domain type to the other; the second is that most FHE schemes involve "ciphertext maintenance operations", such as modulus switching, key switching, and rescaling, which involve non-algebraic operations (operations that are not native to both of the aforementioned types of algebraic domain) such as real division and rounding.

Unfortunately, our general assessment after our work in [27] is still that even for simple ML models, the state-of-the-art in the topic of verifiable computation is still far from providing a practical solution to this problem, and therefore it will require

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more effort of the cryptographic research community in the next years to significantly improve the efficiency of this type of protocols.

Indeed, in our now state-of-the-art new verifiable computation for CKKS encryption protocol, we estimate proving the correct computation of one multiplication takes around 25 seconds. In contrast, even a small FHE-friendly Neural Network model such as CryptoNets [29] requires 1520 multiplications per inference, which, according to our estimates, would take 10h30m to be proven. For comparison, this represents 3 orders of magnitude overhead over FHE without verification, since homomorphically evaluating this encrypted inference takes around 20 seconds (see Table 2). As we advance in this line of work, we have been developing methods for improving the scalability of our techniques. In particular, we expect the performance of an actual end-to-end verifiable FHE solution based on our techniques to be much better than the estimates we provide, as we assume many worst-case scenarios when computing them. Moreover, the question of verifiability of FHE-encrypted data, and its application in particular to ML use cases, is currently a very actively researched one within the cryptographic community, so many improvements are expected in the next years that bring the applications closer to being practical.

4.2 VERIFIABILITY IN FEDERATED LEARNING

As discussed in the previous section, verifiable FHE is currently not mature enough for ML applications. Therefore, other approaches have to be considered as well, such as Federated Learning (FL).

Federated learning is an area of AI that aims to provide some privacy when several parties want to collaboratively train an AI model on their data. Naively, all the parties could simply send their data to a central entity, which would train a global model and send that model to all participating parties. However, in this approach the central entity – which may or may not be one of the parties – will then see all of the data, which may not be desirable. Federated learning takes a slightly different approach. Rather than all parties sending their data to a central entity, they instead each train a model on their local data. After some number of local training batches, each party sends their model parameters to the central entity, which aggregates all received parameters in some way to arrive at an overarching, global model. The central entity then sends this global model back to all parties. They will then update it based on their next batches, leading to an iterative process in which the global model's quality will keep improving. While federated learning does not provide privacy as strong as cryptographic methods like FHE, it is considered a viable alternative in certain contexts.

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However, the federated setting encounters a number of potential issues, including the following:

1. How can parties verify that the central entity performed the parameter aggregation in the right way?
2. How can parties verify that the other parties performed the right training steps and provided the right model parameters to the central entity?
3. How can parties verify that the other parties performed their training on the right data?

During this project, we have investigated how these challenges can be addressed by adding verifiability components. In particular, we investigated how to add (different types of) zero-knowledge proofs to the entire federated learning pipeline. While the first point is relatively easy, the second point is more complex. For the third point, we consider external, trusted auditing parties that *can* see and sign the data, so that the other parties can verify based on this signature. Unfortunately, this line of work is still ongoing at the time of writing, so we are presently unable to point to a concrete paper or implementation.

5 USE CASES

5.1 USE CASE 1: DATA STORED IN MULTIPLE PARTIES

In this section the use of ML models will be covered, while securing the confidentiality of the data that are being generated and stored in multiple other party locations e.g., vehicles, manufacturers, aviation companies, etc., by not sharing the data to a centralized party and by encrypting all the model-related transmitted information.

In the scope of WP5, in use case 1 “Predictive Maintenance for Airline Consortium” and use case 3 “Intelligent Connected Vehicle, FL/ML and Vehicle to Infrastructure Communication” a first implementation of a federated learning framework has been performed. This framework aims to facilitate knowledge exchange while preserving data privacy, in different scenarios involving the operation of airplane engines, the predictive maintenance for car engines (in use case 1) as well as deriving insights about drivers' behaviour, traffic or road infrastructure (in use case 3). This initial implementation, described in more details in D5.1 “Pilot Requirements Definition and Integration report” [30], tries to leverage federated learning to analyse sensitive data without exposing it in its raw form. The first implementation focused on Random Forest Classification.

While FL does provide some measure of privacy, it is hard to quantify this and strong privacy guarantees can generally not be made. For instance, the model parameters sent from a client to the central server may leak information about the client's dataset. To mitigate this, a next step could be to combine FL with homomorphic encryption. In a nutshell, the idea is that the clients encrypt their model parameters before sending them to the central server. The model aggregation is then performed by the central server in the encrypted domain, after which the encrypted global model is sent back to the clients. However, in order for the clients to be able to decrypt, some nuance is required. We cannot allow all parties to have the same private key, as this would undermine the security of the entire protocol. Rather, a possible solution would involve threshold homomorphic encryption, with a single public key and a different, but correlated, private key for each client. With such a scheme, any client can encrypt their model parameters using the public key. However, decryption is only possible if all (or some threshold t) clients collaborate. This way, the clients can decrypt the global model together, without being able to decrypt each other's local models.

Figure 4: Visualization dashboard for Predictive maintenance for airline consortium using federated AI/ML: Visualization of various parameters for diverse aircrafts.

This process can be repeated iteratively to refine the global model over multiple communication rounds. By analysing operational data, the overall system can provide predictive maintenance alerts, warning aircraft operators and automobile manufacturers about potential engine failures before they occur (in the scope of use case 1, Figure 4). Similarly, in the case of driving behaviour analysis (for use case 3, Figure 5), the system can identify risky driving patterns or road infrastructure issues and provide feedback to enhance road safety. These insights contribute to improved operational efficiency, reduced maintenance costs, and enhanced safety standards across aviation and automotive industries. Especially with respect to the work in use case 3, related to deriving insights on road infrastructure status and driving behaviour, effort has been made to integrate with commercial products with cameras and On Board Units (OBUs) in commercial

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deployments. In this context an additional HistGradientBoosting model has been applied and tested in these commercial deployments for Driving Style Prediction (Aggressive vs. Normal). The combination of FHE with Random Forest classification and other types of decision tree models can have impacts on the accuracy and more importantly, for the application with real time data, on the execution time [31]. Work is currently ongoing on the combination of FHE with the learning mechanisms originally developed and the evaluation of the corresponding performance. Potentially other types of models may need to be employed such as logistic regression. The aim is to present more concrete results on this work in the scope of the forthcoming Deliverable D5.2 “Pilot execution report”.

Figure 5. Visualisation dashboard for deriving traffic and driving style behaviour using federated AI/ML: Visualisation of various parameters for diverse vehicles

5.2 USE CASE 2: SECURE APP PLACEMENT IN MULTI-STAKEHOLDER NETWORK

In what follows, we will describe a use case in which FHE can be used to perform a type of calculation in a 6G setting. For a precise consideration of the use case, we refer to Deliverable 2.3. Moreover, we note that we abstract away from a specific FHE algorithm here: the point is more to illustrate how FHE can be used to tackle problems of this kind.

5.2.1 NOTATION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

As described in Deliverable D2.3, we consider a multi-stakeholder network in which some entity wants to run an application (App) with minimal delay towards a user device (U). The delay will depend on the placement of the App (i.e. which stakeholder) and the paths available between the App and U. Some stakeholders ("edge clouds") have relatively little computing power but can connect to the user device directly, so the transmission delay is small. Other stakeholders have more computing power, and thus running the App there would give little delay, but they can only connect to the user device through several other intermediate networks, causing more transmission delay. Overall, the means the multi-stakeholder network forms what is called a *cloud continuum* – an expected aspect of future 6G networks.

In order to calculate where to best put the App, each stakeholder has to provide information about their computing power and transmission delays to other stakeholders. However, this might imply information about their current load or business processes, which they would rather keep secret. Our goal is then to perform this optimization task a secure, i.e. privacy respecting way.

As mathematical model for the use case, we consider a graph $G = (V', E)$, where V' is the set of nodes, and $E \subseteq V' \times V'$ is the set of edges with $(i, j) \in E$ denoting the existence of an edge from node i to node j . Here $V' = V \cup \{U\}$, with V denoting the set of stakeholder networks and U denoting the user device that we want to connect to. Furthermore, we consider the graph to be in a specific structure where it can be viewed as a series of layers $V_k \subseteq V$ for $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ and any node can only have an edge to or from a node in a layer either directly preceding or following its own layer (where preceding means lower k and following means higher k), see Figure 6. This models the architecture of 6G, with the aforementioned cloud continuum: "near edge" networks will connect to user (edge) devices on one side (the node U in the figure) and to "far edge" networks on the other side, and this trend continues through of sequence of layers, ending at the core or own network (V_K in Figure 6).

Figure 6: Illustration of the network structure.

The black dots represent nodes, clustered vertically in layers, and connected to nodes in neighboring layers. The user node is all the way on the right, while the most central network node is all the way to the left. The blue highlighted lines represent the downstream connections from node i in layer V_k (highlighted in blue), to the nodes j in layer V_{k-1} .

Note: we will assume that any two adjacent layers V_k and V_{k+1} form a complete bipartite graph, meaning that every node in V_k has an edge to every node in V_{k+1} . The reason for this assumption is that it allows for a cleaner presentation in this proof of concept. Moreover, what follows is easily generalized to non-complete settings, at the expense of some minor additional details and notation.

In the model, we consider two types of delay. For any $i \in V$, we let $D_L(i)$ denote the delay within stakeholder network i caused by the current (computational) load it is processing. Furthermore, for any $(i, j) \in E$ we let $D_T(i, j)$ denote the delay in the transmission link between i and j . For our purposes, we are often interested in the total delay when connecting node i to node j , which we take to be the sum of the internal delay in i and the delay over the transmission link. Hence, we define the weight or the total delay by setting $D(i, j) = D_L(i) + D_T(i, j)$. Next, we make a distinction between the delays in the network *without* considering placement of the app, versus with placement of the app *at a specific node* $i \in V$:

- $A(i)$: minimal network delay between node i and the user node U , without considering placement of the app. More formally, we set:

$$A(i) := \min\{\sum_{(m,n) \in p} D(m, n) \mid p \in \mathcal{P}(i, U)\}$$

where $\mathcal{P}(i, U)$ denotes the set of all paths from node i to U (with a path being a set of connected edges).

NB: Note that for any $i \in V_k$, there will be a specific path p associated with the optimum $A(i)$. In particular, there will be some $j \in V_{k-1}$ such that (i, j) is on this path. We will denote this j by $v_{\min}(i)$. That is, for any $i \in V_k$, we write $v_{\min}(i)$ for the node in the preceding layer that lies on the optimal path.

- $A^*(i)$: minimal network delay between node i and the user node U , if the app is placed at node i . Writing $D_A(i)$ for the extra delay incurred over node i when placing the app there, we have $A^*(i) = A(i) + D_A(i)$ for any node $i \in V$.

Goal: We want to find v^* , which is defined as

$$v^* := \arg \min_{i \in V} A^*(i)$$

that is, the node in the network such that when placing the app there, the total delay to the user device U is minimal. Note that in order to find v^* , we will also calculate

$$A_{\min}^* := \min_{i \in V} A^*(i).$$

In order to find A_{\min}^* , we will need to calculate $A^*(i)$ at every $i \in V$. Rather than taking the minimum over all these $A^*(i)$ directly, we will proceed through the graph in a structured way, taking intermediate minima. To that end, we introduce another piece of notation. Specifically, we write $B^*(i)$ for the minimum of $A^*(i)$ and all $A^*(j)$ for nodes j that fall on a path between i and U . Intuitively, $B^*(i)$ will represent the best minimum so far, as discovered up to node i . Due to the structure of our graph and algorithm, we can calculate $B^*(i)$ by taking $B^*(i) = \min(\{A^*(i)\} \cup \{B^*(j) | j \in V_{k-1}\})$: the minimum-so-far at node i (i.e. $B^*(i)$) is the minimum of the value at i (i.e. $A^*(i)$) and the minima-so-far at the previous layer (i.e. $\{B^*(i) | i \in V_{k-1}\}$).

5.2.2 APPROACH

For any node i in layer V_k , in order to calculate $A(i)$, it is both necessary and sufficient to know $A(j)$ for all $j \in V_{k-1}$, and thus requires some input from those j . Once a given node i knows $A(i)$, it only requires a local operation to calculate $A^*(i)$. As such, we propose an algorithm in which information propagates back and forth through the graph and minima and calculated intermediate stages, with the minimum (so far) being passed on to the next layer towards the left. Intuitively, algorithm is structured in the following way:

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- (“←”): Starting at the layer closest to U and moving towards higher layers, we take the following steps. For each $i \in V_k$, use the received values $\{A(j) | j \in V_{k-1}\}$ to calculate $\min_{j \in V_{k-1}} \{A(j) + D(i, j)\}$ and note that this value equals $A(i)$. Denote the associated node (i.e. the j achieving the minimum) in the previous layer by $v_{\min}(i)$. Then, compute $A^*(i)$ by adding $A(i)$ and $D_A(i)$. Now, take the minimum of $A^*(i)$ and the received values $\{B^*(j) | j \in V_{k-1}\}$ to find $B^*(i)$, the minimum-so-far (i.e. best-app-placement-so-far). Store $A^*(i)$ and $v_{\min}(i)$ locally and send $A(i)$ and $B^*(i)$ to all nodes in the next layer.
- (“.”): At the highest layer $V_K = \{v_K\}$, we now know the value of:

$$B^*(v_K) = \min(\{A^*(v_K)\} \cup \{B^*(i) | i \in V_{K-1}\}) = \min_{i \in V} A^*(i) = A_{\min}^*$$

So at this point, the minimum delay is known. However, this information needs to be propagated back through the graph in order to find out which node $i \in V_k$ achieves this minimum (i.e. which node is v^*) – and what the optimal path from that node to U is. This is done in the final step. 3.

- (“→”): Starting at layer V_K and moving towards lower- k layers, pass on the value A_{\min}^* to all nodes in the lower layer. Each node i will compare the received A_{\min}^* to their locally saved $A^*(i)$. If those two differ, then node i is not the optimal app placement site and they will pass on A_{\min}^* to the next lower- k layer. However, if A_{\min}^* and $A^*(i)$ are equal, then node i is the optimal app placement node v^* we are looking for. In this case, they will run the app. Furthermore, they will reach out to $j = v_{\min}(i)$ to alert them to the fact that they are on the optimal path. This node will in turn reach out to $j' = v_{\min}(j)$ to alert them that they are also on the optimal path, et cetera.

At this point, we emphasize that this three-point protocol sketch only describes the functionality we are looking for. It requires sharing a lot of sensitive data (namely: properties of the stakeholder networks) between different nodes, which is undesirable. In the next section, we will detail how to perform this protocol *securely*.

5.2.3 PROOF OF CONCEPT

In what follows, we propose a solution to perform the required calculations for the stated problem in a secure way. That is: we do not want any of the nodes to learn anything about the other nodes' delays. To achieve this, we suggest an approach using Threshold Fully Homomorphic Encryption (ThFHE). More particularly, we consider a 2-threshold FHE scheme. This means that no party can decrypt a ciphertext by themselves, but any 2 parties in the consortium can collaborate to decrypt something. Note that Threshold FHE requires some kind of distributed key

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generation (DKG), which we have done some work on in the Deliverable 2.3. Although we have mainly considered DKG for discrete-log-based schemes (hence not FHE), we do have one component which is post-quantum and more generic, and we want to develop in the future DKG based on that, which could be applied to this setting.

The idea is that using such a 2-threshold scheme, any party can encrypt sensitive values and pass these on to other nodes to perform computations on, without risking that other node decrypting and retrieving their sensitive information. At the same time, due to the 2-thresholdness, nodes are able to ask a neighboring node to assist in decryption whenever the algorithm prescribes it, e.g. to find out whether a given node is the optimal place for the App or not. Note that we could also use a different threshold t , giving a more robust protocol at the expense of extra communication.

Generally, the idea of our algorithm is that all nodes encrypt their local delays and collaboratively calculate the optimal delay in the encrypted domain. Since no party can decrypt on their own, the sensitive information stays secret. When the minimum delay has been found, some decryptions are necessary to find v^* and alert the nodes in the optimal path. Indeed, for these decryptions, the 2-thresholdness is used and the relevant nodes will ask a neighboring node to help decrypt.

So, in our setting, each node will have a private key sk_i and there will be single public key pk . We will assume the ThFHE scheme supports a number of building blocks, listed below.

Note: To emphasize that a variable x is encrypted, we will write $\langle x \rangle$. However, when an encrypted variable is used as input for a function, we will leave out the $\langle \rangle$ to avoid notational clutter.

- $\langle c \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE. Enc}(pk, m)$: Given some m , encrypt it using the public key. Anybody (with access to the public key) can perform this. Since there is only a single public key which will be known to everyone, we will often suppress the pk in notation.
- $\langle \sigma_i \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE. PartDec}(\langle c \rangle, sk_i)$: Given a ciphertext $\langle c \rangle$, any party i can use their private key to find a partial decryption $\langle \sigma_i \rangle$. Note that this partial decryption by itself leaks nothing about the underlying plaintext.
- $m \leftarrow \text{FHE. FinDec}(\langle \sigma_i \rangle, \langle \sigma_j \rangle)$: Given two partial decryptions $\langle \sigma_i \rangle$ and $\langle \sigma_j \rangle$ of the same ciphertext, combine them for a full decryption to a plaintext m . Note that we require two partial decryptions because our scheme is 2-threshold.

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- $\langle c \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Add}(\langle c_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle c_k \rangle)$: Given ciphertexts $\langle c_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle c_k \rangle$, calculate the ciphertext $\langle c \rangle$ such that the decryption of $\langle c \rangle$ equals the sum of the decryptions of $\langle c_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle c_k \rangle$.
- $\langle c \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Mult}(\langle c_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle c_k \rangle)$: Given ciphertexts $\langle c_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle c_k \rangle$, calculate the ciphertext $\langle c \rangle$ such that the decryption of c equals the product of the decryptions of $\langle c_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle c_k \rangle$. Note that we will not use FHE.Mult directly, but we list it for the sake of completeness.
- $\langle c \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Min}(\langle c_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle c_k \rangle)$: Given ciphertexts $\langle c_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle c_k \rangle$, calculate the ciphertext $\langle c \rangle$ such that the decryption of $\langle c \rangle$ equals the minimum of the decryptions of $\langle c_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle c_k \rangle$.
- $\langle c \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Eq}(\langle c_1 \rangle, \langle c_2 \rangle)$: Given two ciphertexts $\langle c_1 \rangle, \langle c_2 \rangle$, calculates a ciphertext $\langle c \rangle$, which decrypts to 1 if the decryption of $\langle c_1 \rangle$ equals the decryption of $\langle c_2 \rangle$ and which decrypts to 0 otherwise (i.e. if $\langle c_1 \rangle$ and $\langle c_2 \rangle$ have different underlying plaintexts).

Algorithm: step 1

The goal of this first step coincides with the functionality described in (“ \leftarrow ”): to find the minimum delay $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$ (NB: in encrypted form) for placing the app in the network. In order to find this, we work from U on the right hand side of the graph to V_K on the left. For each layer V_k with $k > 1$, all nodes i in the layer will receive encrypted values $\langle A(j) \rangle$ and $\langle B^*(j) \rangle$ from all nodes j in the previous layer V_{k-1} . They will locally encrypt their own values and perform the required calculations to find:

- $\langle A(i) \rangle$, which is a ciphertext representing the shortest path from i to U .
- $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle$, which is a ciphertext representing the node $j \in V_{k-1}$ through which this shortest path runs.
- $\langle A^*(i) \rangle$, which is a ciphertext representing the total delay to U if one were to place the app at i .
- $\langle B^*(i) \rangle$, which is a ciphertext representing the total delay for the best app placement so far (i.e. on all nodes between i and U , including i itself). That is, the minimum value for $A^*(j)$ where $j \in (U_{\ell < k} V_\ell) \cup \{i\}$.

Then, the values $\langle A^*(i) \rangle$ and $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle$ are stored locally until their use in step 2. The values $\langle A(i) \rangle$ and $\langle B^*(i) \rangle$ are sent to all nodes in V_{k+1} , who will then perform the same sequence of calculations. The final layer V_K only contains a single node v_K . By structure of the algorithm, the value $\langle B^*(v_K) \rangle$ then represents the total delay for the best app placement in the entire graph. To emphasize this, we define $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle := \langle B^*(v_K) \rangle$, which is where this step terminates.

Note that no decryptions occur in this step at all. We refer to the pseudocode in Algorithm 1 for the details.

Algorithm: step 2

Given the output $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$ from step 1, we continue with the second and final step. The goal here is to determine the optimal node v^* , place the app there, and communicate this to all relevant nodes in the optimal path from v^* to U . See the pseudocode in Algorithm 2 for the details. We introduce three pieces of notation: for any node $i \in V$, we let $v^*(i)$ denote the boolean value of the statement “ i is the node for optimal app placement v^* ”. Furthermore, for a node $i \in V_k$ on the optimal path between v^* and the user device U , we write $v_{\text{up}}(i)$ for the node $j \in V_{k+1}$ that is also on the optimal path, i.e. to which it has to connect when the app is run. Similarly, we write $v_{\text{down}}(i)$ for the node $\ell \in V_{k-1}$ that is also on the optimal path. Note that $v_{\text{down}}(i)$ will coincide with the $v_{\min}(i)$ as calculated in step 1.

At a high level, we will move through the layers of the graph like in step 1, but now we will go in the opposite direction: starting at the left-most layer $V_K = \{v_K\}$ and moving towards lower- k layers. Each node i in some layer $k < K$ will collect the messages it gets from the layer left of it (i.e. V_{k+1}). Three options exist:

- It might be the case that i receives no messages from any $j \in V_{k+1}$. In this case, node i will simply do nothing: it means that the optimal app placement v^* has been identified and that i is not on the optimal path between v^* and U .
- It might be the case that i receives $\text{msg}(j) = \text{"IN_PATH"}$ from some $j \in V_{k+1}$. This means that the optimal app placement v^* has been found (either in j or in some higher- k layer) and that i is on the optimal path between v^* and U . Furthermore, i knows that j is on this path as well, and will set $v_{\text{up}}(i) = j$. Next, i needs to figure out which $\ell \in V_{k-1}$ to connect to in the other direction. Note that this is, by definition, the node saved locally as $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle$. However, this value is encrypted. Now, the 2-thresholdness of the scheme is used. Node i will ask the node $j = v_{\text{up}}(i)$ to help decrypt $v_{\min}(i)$ in order to set $v_{\text{down}}(i) = v_{\min}(i)$ and send "IN_PATH" to it.
- It might be the case that i receives $\text{msg}(j) = \langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$. This means that i should check, using $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$, whether they are the optimal app placement node v^* . Note that *if* i is the optimal app placement node, then $A_{\min}^* = A^*(i)$ by definition. However, both these values are only available under encryption. So, i will select a random node $j \in V_{k+1}$ to help decrypt the value $\langle e \rangle = \text{FHE.Eq}(\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle, \langle A^*(i) \rangle)$. If $e == 1$, then $i = v^*$ and i will proceed like in the previous scenario to find $v_{\text{down}}(i) = v_{\min}(i)$ and send "IN_PATH" to that node. If $e == 0$, then $i \neq v^*$ and it sends on $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$ to all nodes in V_{k-1} .

NB: In Algorithm 2, a node can only pass on two types of information to the right. Either it passes on "IN_PATH" to the next node in the optimal path, or it passes on

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$\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$. Ideally, a third option "STOP" might be introduced to tell relevant nodes to stop the process when it is clear they are not in the optimal path, but we left this out of the pseudocode to make it more accessible.

```

1: # Start: special case for the first layer  $V_1$ 
2: for  $i \in V_1$  do
3:    $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Enc}(U)$ 
4:    $\langle A(i) \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Enc}(D(i, U))$ 
5:    $\langle A^*(i) \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Enc}(A(i) + D_A(i))$ 
6:    $\langle B^*(i) \rangle \leftarrow \langle A^*(i) \rangle$ 
7:
8:   save  $\langle A^*(i) \rangle$  and  $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle$  locally.
9:   send  $[\langle A(i) \rangle, \langle B^*(i) \rangle]$  to all  $j \in V_{k+1}$ 
10: end for
11:
12: # All other layers
13: for  $k = 2, \dots, K$  do
14:   for  $i \in V_k$  do
15:     for  $j \in V_{k-1}$  do
16:       receive  $[\langle A(j) \rangle, \langle B^*(j) \rangle]$ 
17:        $\langle D(i, j) \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Enc}(D(i, j))$ 
18:        $\langle T(i, j) \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Add}(\langle A(j) \rangle, \langle D(i, j) \rangle)$   $\triangleright \text{min. dist. } i \rightarrow j \rightarrow U$ 
19:     end for
20:      $\langle A(i) \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Min}(\{\langle T(i, j) \rangle\}_{j \in V_{k-1}})$   $\triangleright \text{min. dist. } i \rightarrow U$ 
21:      $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle \leftarrow \sum_{j \in V_{k-1}} (\text{FHE.Eq}(\langle A(i) \rangle, \langle T(i, j) \rangle) \cdot \text{FHE.Enc}(k))$   $\triangleright \text{argmin}$ 
22:      $\langle A^*(i) \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Add}(\langle A(i) \rangle, \text{FHE.Enc}(D_A(i)))$ 
23:      $\langle B^*(i) \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Min}(\{\langle B^*(j) \rangle\}_{j \in V_{k-1}})$ 
24:      $\langle B^*(i) \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Min}(\langle B^*(i) \rangle, \langle A^*(i) \rangle)$ 
25:     save  $\langle A^*(i) \rangle$  and  $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle$  locally.
26:     if  $k \neq K$  then  $\triangleright \text{pass on data only if not in highest layer}$ 
27:       send  $[\langle A(i) \rangle, \langle B^*(i) \rangle]$  to all  $j \in V_{k+1}$ 
28:     end if
29:   end for
30: end for
31:
32: return  $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle = \langle B^*(v_K) \rangle$   $\triangleright \text{by assumption } V_K = \{v_K\}$ 

```

Algorithm 1: Secure algorithm to find the minimum network delay $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$

```

1: # Start: special case for the leftmost layer  $V_K$ 
2: # Recall that  $V_K = \{v_K\}$  by assumption
3: let  $j \in V_{K-1}$  be arbitrary ▷ to help with decrypting
4:  $\langle e \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Eq}(A_{\min}^*, A^*(v_K))$ 
5:  $\tau_i \leftarrow \text{FHE.PartDec}(e, \text{sk}_{v_K})$ 
6: send  $\langle e \rangle$  to  $j$ ; receive  $\tau_j = \text{FHE.PartDec}(e, \text{sk}_j)$ 
7:  $e \leftarrow \text{FHE.FinDec}(\tau_i, \tau_j)$ 
8: if  $e == 1$  then ▷  $v_K$  is  $v^*$ ; start optimal path
9:    $v^*(v_K) \leftarrow \text{True}$ 
10:   $\sigma_K \leftarrow \text{FHE.PartDec}(v_{\min}(v_K), \text{sk}_{v_K})$ 
11:  send  $\langle v_{\min}(v_K) \rangle$  to  $j$ ; receive  $\sigma_j = \text{FHE.PartDec}(v_{\min}(v_K), \text{sk}_j)$ 
12:   $v_{\text{down}}(v_K) \leftarrow \text{FHE.FinDec}(\sigma_K, \sigma_j)$ 
13:  send "IN_PATH" to  $v_{\text{down}}(v_K)$ 
14: else
15:   send  $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$  to all  $j \in V_{K-1}$ 
16: end if
17:
18: # Work through rest of layers from high-to-low layer numbers
19: for  $k = K - 1, \dots, 1$  do
20:   for  $i \in V_k$  do
21:     receive msg( $j$ ) from some subset  $J \subset V_{k+1}$  ▷ Not all  $j$  might send
22:     set  $S(i) \leftarrow \{\text{msg}(j) \mid j \in J\}$ 
23:
24:     if  $S(i) == \emptyset$  then ▷  $i$  is not involved in optimal path
25:       continue to next node in  $V_k$ 
26:
27:     else if "IN_PATH"  $\in S(i)$  then ▷ in optimal path! (but app elsewhere)
28:       ▷ Goal: find next node in path, i.e. decrypt  $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle$ 
29:       let  $j \in J$  be such that msg( $j$ ) = "IN_PATH"
30:        $\sigma_i \leftarrow \text{FHE.PartDec}(v_{\min}(i), \text{sk}_i)$ 
31:        $v_{\text{up}}(i) \leftarrow j$ 
32:       send  $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle$  to  $j$ ; receive  $\sigma_j = \text{FHE.PartDec}(v_{\min}(i), \text{sk}_j)$ 
33:        $v_{\text{down}}(i) \leftarrow \text{FHE.FinDec}(\sigma_i, \sigma_j)$ 
34:       send "IN_PATH" to  $v_{\text{down}}(i)$ 
35:
36:     else ▷ i.e. msg( $j$ ) ==  $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$  for all  $j \in J$ ; so  $v^*$  is not yet found
37:       ▷ Goal: check whether  $i$  is  $v^*$ ; pass on to next layer otherwise
38:       let  $j \in J$  be arbitrary ▷ to help with decrypting
39:        $\langle e \rangle \leftarrow \text{FHE.Eq}(A_{\min}^*, A^*(i))$ 
40:        $\tau_i \leftarrow \text{FHE.PartDec}(e, \text{sk}_i)$ 
41:       send  $\langle e \rangle$  to  $j$ ; receive  $\tau_j = \text{FHE.PartDec}(e, \text{sk}_j)$ 
42:        $e \leftarrow \text{FHE.FinDec}(\tau_i, \tau_j)$ 
43:       if  $e == 1$  then ▷  $i$  is  $v^*$ ; start optimal path
44:          $v^*(i) \leftarrow \text{True}$ 
45:          $\sigma_i \leftarrow \text{FHE.PartDec}(v_{\min}(i), \text{sk}_i)$ 
46:         send  $\langle v_{\min}(i) \rangle$  to  $j$ ; receive  $\sigma_j = \text{FHE.PartDec}(v_{\min}(i), \text{sk}_j)$ 
47:          $v_{\text{down}}(i) \leftarrow \text{FHE.FinDec}(\sigma_i, \sigma_j)$ 
48:         send "IN_PATH" to  $v_{\text{down}}(i)$ 
49:       else ▷  $i$  is not  $v^*$  and not part of optimal path
50:         send  $\langle A_{\min}^* \rangle$  to all  $j \in V_{k-1}$ 
51:       end if
52:     end if
53:   end for
54: end for

```

Algorithm 2: Secure algorithm to place app in optimal node v^*

6 CONCLUSIONS

This document was written to provide an overview of the research done in Task 3.3 of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. In particular, this task focuses on the relation between privacy enhancing technologies (PETs) on one side and machine learning (or artificial intelligence more broadly) on the other. We zoomed in on three PETs specifically: Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) and the use of cryptographic proofs for verifiability. We note that all of these PETs were also the topic of Deliverable 2.3. Indeed, D2.3 can be considered a companion piece to the present deliverable, with the difference that the present deliverable focuses on applications of these PETs to AI.

By combining TEEs with AI, users are able to train their AI models on sensitive data, without revealing this sensitive data. We describe how the different components of a TEE interact to achieve this in Section 2. In some sense, FHE serves a similar purpose within an AI context. However, rather than the hardware-based solution TEEs offer, FHE allows for training and evaluating machine learning models using a software or mathematics based approach. We discuss this at length in Section 3. While e.g. TEEs and FHE both offer great improvements in terms of confidentiality, this does not immediately solve all of the issues associated with AI use. Indeed, another important consideration revolves around *verifiability*: how can a user ensure that a third party (e.g. cloud service provider) uses their data as agreed upon? Even if measures for confidentiality (such as FHE) have been taken, this remains a challenge. One solution is to involve cryptographic proofs, and we explore this topic of verifiable computing in Section 4. Note that while verifiability is mature in certain applications, there remain significant challenges for applications to (large scale) AI.

In the final chapter, we take a more concrete approach and consider how PETs can be used in practice. Indeed, we explore two use cases in detail in which advanced PETs can enable functionalities that were hitherto not realistic.

All in all, we show that PETs are an extremely useful concept in the context of AI, though some advancement of the technologies is still required for large scale deployment.

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DRAFT

APPENDIX A : TEST CASES

In this deliverable, we discussed a number of privacy enhancing technologies: TEE, FHE and (Z)KP. For each of these technologies, some *test cases* were developed, which are of broader interest in the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. In particular, testing in a pilot operation falls within the scope of WP5 for use case 1 and use case 2. For the sake of completeness, we will elaborate the tests here, as they are relevant to the technologies at hand.

Testing in this context refers to the evaluation of components taking into account specified functional platform requirements. The goal is to identify and rectify bugs, deficiencies, unexpected behavior and to timely provide corrective measures. We should stress the fact that the testing procedures described in this deliverable will be performed on a technical level, by the development teams of the project themselves and not by real users.

Testing in a pilot operation of the platform falls within the scope of WP5 for use case 1 and use case 2 and will be elaborated there.

Testing is, usually, performed on two levels:

- i) Individual module
- ii) Integrated system testing.

The former refers to the testing of the individual system components with respect to the requirements and the latter refers to the testing of the integrated system itself by assessing the interfaces among the modules and the involved data flow and the expected behavior of the system “as a whole.”

In order to effectively manage the complexity of the final system, testing will be initially performed on an individual module basis before the integration begins. After all modules are verified, then the integration will begin and when it is completed, a final set of tests will be performed mainly in the form of a small-scale pilot operation.

Table 4: Test case: Verify TEE prevents access to confidential input data

Test case id:	WP3_T3.3_TC-01
Test case name:	Verify TEE prevents access to confidential input data
Use case	Use case-2
Partners involved in testing	UVC, VTT
Actors:	Data Provider/Participating Party (provides data), Central Party (executes computation within TEE), TEE System, System Administrator (monitors central party environment).
Description:	Verify that the central party cannot access confidential input data when a TEE is used for computation.
Trigger:	The Data Provider initiates an AI/ML evaluation request, submitting confidential data to the Central Party, configured to use a TEE.
Preconditions:	TEE environment is securely provisioned, configured, and operational on the Central Party's infrastructure.
Postconditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The AI/ML computation completes successfully within the TEE. • The raw input data remains completely inaccessible and unobservable to processes running outside the TEE. • Only encrypted data or computation results are visible/transmitted outside the TEE.
Normal Flow:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Provider encrypts and submits confidential input data to the Central Party. • Central Party's application loads the encrypted data. • The TEE environment securely loads the data (which is then decrypted <i>only inside the TEE</i>). • The specified AI/ML algorithm executes entirely within the TEE using the decrypted data. • Throughout the computation, external monitoring tools attempt to capture data from the Central Party's host memory, disk, and network interfaces. • The TEE securely outputs the computation result (re-encrypted) to the Central Party's application. • The Central Party's application transmits the result back to the Data Provider.

Exceptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the TEE fails to initialize securely, the computation should be aborted, and no sensitive data should be processed. • If monitoring tools detect any raw input data outside the TEE, the test fails immediately, indicating a critical security vulnerability. • If the AI/ML algorithm fails inside the TEE, the TEE should terminate cleanly without exposing intermediate data.
Includes:	TEE Setup Verification, Data Encryption/Decryption Modules.
Assumptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The TEE itself is cryptographically sound and correctly implemented. • Data is properly encrypted <i>before</i> reaching the TEE boundary from the Data Provider's side.

Table 5: Test case: Verify AI/ML evaluation on FHE-encrypted data

Test case id:	WP3_T3.3_TC-02
Test case name:	Verify AI/ML evaluation on FHE-encrypted data
Use case:	Use case 1
Partners involved in testing:	NNF, WIN, UCD
Actors:	Data Provider (encrypts data), Central Party (computes on ciphertext)
Description:	Verify that an AI/ML algorithm can be successfully evaluated on FHE-encrypted data, and the central party cannot decrypt intermediate data.
Trigger:	The Data Provider submits FHE-encrypted confidential data for AI/ML evaluation to the Central Party.
Preconditions:	Not applicable
Postconditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Central Party successfully performs the AI/ML computation directly on the ciphertext. • No plaintext data is accessible or exposed to the Central Party at any point during computation. • The Central Party only handles ciphertext.
Normal Flow:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Provider encrypts confidential input data using the specified FHE scheme.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The encrypted data (ciphertext) is submitted to the Central Party. The Central Party's application receives the ciphertext. The Central Party executes the adapted AI/ML algorithm operations directly on this ciphertext. The Central Party produces a final ciphertext representing the computed result.
Exceptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If the Central Party manages to decrypt any part of the data, the test fails critically. If the FHE computation produces an invalid ciphertext (detectable upon later decryption), it indicates an FHE implementation or algorithm adaptation error. If FHE computation is excessively slow, it highlights a challenge for practical deployment (further detailed in Efficiency tests).
Includes:	FHE Library Integration, Data Encryption Module.
Assumptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The underlying FHE scheme is cryptographically secure against known attacks. The FHE implementation correctly handles arithmetic operations on ciphertexts.

Table 6: Test case: Verify correctness of the final FHE-computed result

Test case id:	WP3_T3.3_TC-03
Test case name:	Verify correctness of the final FHE-computed result
Use case	Use case 1
Partners involved in testing	NNF, UCD
Actors:	Data Provider (holds decryption key), Central Party (computes on ciphertext), Independent Verifier (calculates expected result)
Description:	Verify the correctness of the final result after decrypting the FHE-computed ciphertext.
Trigger:	The Central Party returns an FHE-computed ciphertext to the Data Provider.
Preconditions:	The expected outcome of the AI/ML computation on the original plaintext data is pre-calculated by an Independent Verifier.

Postconditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The final ciphertext is successfully decrypted by the Data Provider. The decrypted result precisely matches the expected outcome from plaintext computation.
Normal Flow:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Central Party transmits this final ciphertext back to the Data Provider. The Data Provider uses its private decryption key to decrypt the ciphertext. The decrypted result is compared to the independently pre-calculated expected plaintext result.
Exceptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> if the ciphertext cannot be decrypted, it indicates a corruption during computation or transmission, or an incorrect key. If the decrypted result does not match the expected plaintext outcome, it indicates an error in the FHE computation (e.g., noise overflow, incorrect algorithm adaptation) or an issue with the expected result.
Includes:	FHE Library Integration, Data Encryption Module.
Assumptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pre-calculated expected result is accurate. The FHE scheme's decryption process is correct.

Table 7: Test case: Verify generation of a valid ZKP for a legitimate evaluation

Test case id:	WP3_T3.3_TC-04
Test case name:	Verify generation of a valid ZKP for a legitimate evaluation
Use case	Use case 1
Partners involved in testing	NNF, UCD
Actors:	Primary: Central Party (generates ZKP), Verifying Party (verifies ZKP), ZKP Framework, Data Provider
Description:	Verify that the central party can generate a valid ZKP attesting to the correctness of a legitimate AI/ML evaluation, and that this ZKP can be successfully verified by other parties.
Trigger:	The Central Party completes a legitimate AI/ML evaluation and is instructed to generate a ZKP for the result.

<p>Preconditions:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ZKP framework is fully integrated into the Central Party's system. • A simple AI/ML algorithm (e.g., basic classification, summation) is runnable and has produced a legitimate result. • The Verifying Party has the necessary public parameters or verification keys for the ZKP.
<p>Postconditions:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A valid ZKP is successfully generated by the Central Party. • The ZKP is successfully verified by the Verifying Party. • The correctness of the AI/ML evaluation result is cryptographically proven.
<p>Normal Flow:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central Party performs a legitimate AI/ML evaluation using input data. • Upon completion, the Central Party invokes the ZKP framework to generate a proof (<i>zkpproof</i>) for the correctness of this specific computation and its resulting output (<i>y</i>). • The Central Party transmits the result (<i>y</i>) and the ZKP (<i>zkpproof</i>) to the Verifying Party. • The Verifying Party receives <i>y</i> and <i>zkpproof</i>. • The Verifying Party uses its ZKP verification module to check the validity of <i>zkpproof</i> with respect to <i>y</i> and the underlying computation. • The verification process returns "True" (proof is valid).
<p>Exceptions:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ZKP framework fails to generate a proof (e.g., due to computational limits, internal errors). • The proof generated is legitimate, but the Verifying Party's module incorrectly returns "False." This indicates an error in the verification implementation.
<p>Includes:</p>	<p>ZKP Prover Module, ZKP Verifier Module, Secure Communication.</p>
<p>Assumptions:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ZKP scheme is cryptographically sound and secure.

Table 8: Test case: Verify ZKP framework detects an incorrect (tampered) result

Test case id:	WP3_T3.3_TC-05
Test case name:	Verify ZKP framework detects an incorrect (tampered) result
Use case	Use case -1
Partners involved in testing	NNF, UCD
Actors:	Central Party (malicious, attempts tampering), Verifying Party (detects tampering)
Description:	Verify that the ZKP framework detects an incorrect (tampered) AI/ML evaluation result submitted by a malicious central party.
Trigger:	The Central Party submits a deliberately incorrect AI/ML evaluation result along with an accompanying ZKP.
Preconditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZKP framework is integrated. • A simple AI/ML algorithm is runnable. • The Central Party has a mechanism to deliberately tamper with the AI/ML result after computation but before proof generation. • The Verifying Party has the necessary public parameters/verification keys.
Postconditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ZKP verification process successfully detects the tampering and returns "False."
Normal Flow:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central Party performs an AI/ML evaluation. • The Central Party modifies the computed result (e.g., changes a value). • The Central Party attempts to generate a ZKP for this incorrect (tampered) result, associating it with the original computation. • The Central Party transmits the tampered result and the (attempted) ZKP to the Verifying Party. • The Verifying Party receives the tampered result and ZKP. • The Verifying Party attempts to verify the ZKP. • The verification process returns "False" (proof is invalid).
Exceptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ZKP verification incorrectly returns "True" for a tampered result. This is a critical security failure,

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	indicating a flaw in the ZKP scheme or its implementation.
Includes:	ZKP Verifier Module, Secure Communication.
Assumptions:	

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